

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE USAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: BENEFITS AND CONCERNS

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Abstract: *The need for artificial intelligence (AI) in higher education (HE) has rapidly increased recently alongside the simultaneous raising of new AI tools. Researchers indicate numerous benefits and risks of AI usage in HE for both teachers and students. Therefore, the paper aims to explore the benefits and concerns related to the use of AI in higher education, specifically focusing on its impact on students' learning. The research will be conducted among university students, with a sample drawn from the Republic of Serbia. Descriptive statistical analysis, along with ANOVA or t-tests, will be used to analyze the data collected. The results of the empirical research are expected to reveal both the positive and negative effects of AI usage on students' learning experiences, offering insights into how AI can enhance educational processes and where challenges may arise. The study will be limited to a specific region and sample size, so the results may not accurately reflect what would be found in other educational settings. It is recommended that educators and administrators carefully consider the integration of AI tools into their curricula, ensuring that they complement traditional learning methods while addressing any concerns regarding equity, accessibility, and the potential impact on students' performance.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI), higher education, learning experience.*